

Astronomy 98r: Protostar Analysis in the Perseus Cluster

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Abstract

The first million years of the formation of low mass stars has been described before in the literature, but is still not entirely understood due to minimal observation. The MASSES (Mass Assembly of Stellar Systems and their Evolution with the SMA) observing project intends to paint a more detailed picture than ever before by observing and analyzing of 73 different protostar targets in the Perseus star forming nebula. The research pays special attention to how low mass stars accrete mass during their formation and what observations of the protostellar envelope and outflow can tell us about this process. Using C18O observations of the envelope of the most easily resolved targets in the survey my project looks to find correlation between the the position angle of the envelope and the direction of the stellar outflows, both calculated from the MASSES survey. The results suggest that the model for protostellar outflows role in the formation and shaping of the accretion disk may be large.

1 Introduction

The first million years of the development of a low mass star is very different from the rest of its life as the star has yet to begin the fusion that creates the starlight most commonly used to look at stars. This faze is the collapse of a dense enough region of a dust cloud from a very thin an large envelope of gas down to the resulting star. The collapse caused by gravity heats up the gas and increases the pressure that eventually forms the star. The goal of the MASSES project is to understand the evolution of this gas envelope by observing a variety of protostars in the relatively nearby Perseus Nebula.

Observing the collapsing cloud requires observations of the dust in the envelope which is heating up enough to produce grey body emission in very long wavelengths. The data for this research comes from the Submillimeter Array at Alma. Observations of the targets were taken in a variety of trace gasses (CO, 13CO, C18O, HCO+, H13CO+, N2D+) as well as the continuum. The different trace gasses give more data and are also each good at detecting specific densities of the gas. The observations also traced the outflows from these protostars as spectra of the targets were taken as well. Red and blue shifted light gives a sense of the movement of the cloud around the target, the rotation of the envelope, and the direction of the jets. With this data the project can derive temperature, mass, and shape estimates for the envelope and jets.

The research which set the ground for MASSES was a survey of 9 protostars done in 2006 by Arce and Sargent in 2006 which studied their collapsing envelopes and outflows. From the small sample the survey made some conclusions about the evolutionary stages of the young protostars. By using temperature as an estimation of age (collapsing protostars heat up as they lose gravitational potential energy), their survey as well as MASSES looks at how the protostars change as they age.

In Arce and Sargent (2006) protostars are described in three distinct classes. Class 0 protostars are young cool collapsing gas clouds and are the youngest of the target protostars. These protostars have not yet developed a disk-like shape and the outflow is only beginning. Class 1 protostars are warmer and have begun to form a disk from their previously more globular shape. It is during this part of the collapse that the outflow from the collapsing gas is at its most distinguishable. Class 2 protostars have a more well defined disk shape as the cloud has collapsed. The jets in these stars have also started to dissipate and are less distinct in observations. Arce and Sargent (2006) uses the figure below to visualize these three classes.

Arce and Sargent's model contends that the outflows have a significant impact on the shape of the disk. While the globular shape of the collapsing cloud has little shape in the early protostar, the outflows formed by collapsing dust bouncing back out pushes away the dust and gas in its way. Over the million years of collapse this process pushed material out of the system in the direction of the outflows. Creating a perpendicularity between the outflows and the shape of the collapsing envelope and accretion disk.

As suggested by the figure, the survey hypothesized that the outflow from the protostar grows perpendicular to the forming accretion disk as the star evolves. It is believed that the outflow contributes to the formation of the disk structure by blowing away significant amounts of the dust in its path, leaving the disk-like structure behind. This model predicts that as the protostar evolves the outflow angle helps to shape the disk, so while there may be little correlation between the shape of the envelope and the outflow direction at the beginning of the collapse, by the end they should be nearly perpendicular. My project was to see if our observations were consistent with that hypothesis: to see if younger stars showed a smaller correlation between envelope shape and outflow angle than older protostars that have had longer time to be affected.

2 Methods and Results

The goal of my research within the MASSES data analysis is to see if observations of the envelopes and outflows of the protostars in the Perseus nebula are consistent with the model proposed by Arce and Sargent. The model predicts that as the young protostars evolve their outflow will help to create the accretion disk from the original structure. This means that the angle of the disk should be perpendicular to the angle of the angle of the outflow by the end of their evolution.

From an observational standpoint we can observe a separation angle between the directional angle of the outflows and the position angle of the envelope. If the protostar is oriented in a direction as in figure 1 with respect to Earth the angle of separation should grow towards ninety degrees as the system ages. Un-

Figure 1: Arce and Sargent Protostellar Classifications

Figure 2: Arce and Sargent created the above image to describe the evolution of the protostar.

fortunately the systems are oriented randomly and with only a two dimensional view of both the outflow and the jets some orientations will approach less than ninety purely due to orientation. The expected correlation between age and separation angle is therefore considerably less. However, with the large number of targets from the MASSES project we hoped to find significant correlation.

The target stars are those chosen from the MASSES observations of the Perseus Nebula. The Perseus Nebula at a distance of only 238 parsecs allowed good resolution and a large number of targets. The majority of the 73 target protostars come from analysis of Spitzer SEDs from Enoch et al. (2009) MASSES chose mainly class 0 and class 1 protostars which are good targets for understanding the formation of the disk and the evolution of the outflow.

The outflows are observed best in CO where red and blue shifted emission from the outflows are observed as in figure 2 below. To describe the angle of the outflow a line is traced from the peak of the outflow emission to the center of the envelope and the angle is measured counterclockwise from north. Not all of the targets from MASSES had easily defined outflow angles. Especially in cases of binary protostars where there is overlap of rotation and outflows there is not always a clear angle for the outflow. Therefore not all of the targets had well defined outflow angles and were not used in the final analysis. (Ian Stephens pending published research used for outflow angles.

The position angle of the envelope are measured by fitting an ellipse to the integrated source. The position angle is measured from north counterclockwise

Figure 3: Outflow Observations

Figure 4: CO red and blue shifted gas viewed in the MASSES data

to the axis of the ellipse We used C18O images of the targets which were able to resolve the images on the order of 1000 AU giving good resolution for the envelope shape, although the accretion disk itself was not resolvable. The C18O images are opened in casaviewer and the identified protostars are circled and fit to an elliptical gaussian. Casa outputs both the position angle of the envelope and the error bounds. Similar to the outflows not all targets gave position angle measurements with low error. The targets included in the final analysis below had well resolved C18O envelopes as well as well defined outflow jets, this still left us with a considerable number of targets.

3 Discussion

Using temperatures calculated by Tobin et al. (2016) from the grey body integrated flux from the sources, we can plot how separation angle relates to temperature, separation angle being the difference between the envelopes position angle and the angle of the outflow. Temperature grows with age for these targets so this shows how the angle grows with the age of the star as predicted by the model.

It is evident from the data that there is a trend upward in separation angle, but the correlation with the best attempted fit still is only .33. The question is whether or not this is consistent with the predictions of the model of the trend

Figure 5: Outflow Observations

Figure 6: Appearing to best fit linearly, the degree of separation of the outflow angle and envelope position angle are larger in the older warmer targets

towards 90 degrees given randomly oriented protostars. The error analysis and best means for determining this analysis is my current work. It may be possible to compare our observations to mock data, as to what we would expect from randomly oriented protostars without any trend towards 90 degree separation angle, but rather random separation angles. By comparing our data to such fake data we may get a better sense for the confidence in the correlation we see.

Correlation in the data between the age of the protostars and the separation angle suggests that the model proposed by Arce and Sargent likely holds true to the observations now that MASSES has accumulated enough sources to test the model for the first time. Outflows appear to play a large role in shaping the the forming protostar and may even have more profound affects not yet studied if they are moving mass to the degree necessary to play the role they are playing.

4 Conclusion

There is still analysis to be done of the data discussed in this research paper. However the suggestion of a correlation between age and separation angle means that the model proposed by Arce and Sargent describing outflows that shape the collapsing envelope is likely supported once again.

A next step for future research might be to see if the mass decrease caused by such strong outflows is measureable. It is possible that mass would also decrease with age for protostars due to the same process. There are many future research questions that MASSES is interested in answering relating the changes in mass, shape, age, and outflow of early protostars. The larger sample size of the MASSES survey will hopefully lead to statistical backing of previous

understandings of protostars.

5 Bibliography

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